

Federated Learning for Personalized Recommendation

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Abstract—User experiences are improved by personalized recommendation systems, which have various uses in e-commerce, entertainment, health, etc. But there are privacy and legal problems with the centralized data collection. As an alternative to centralized data collection, Federated Learning (FL) offers model training on user devices. It allows model training without gaining access to personal information. The purpose of this seminar is to showcase FL's potential in personalized recommendations for shopping, healthcare, and content delivery. Prescriptive analytics combined with federated learning can help pet owners adopt pets while protecting their privacy, as demonstrated by a PETNOVA case study. There are issues with algorithm performance, fairness, and model heterogeneity that will be covered. Also go over the future developments of hybrid learning, secure aggregation, and differential privacy.

Keywords—Federated Learning, Privacy-Preserving AI, Recommendation Systems, Security, Personalization

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems are advantageous in improving experiences in numerous domains such as e-commerce, entertainment, and healthcare. Recommendation systems have also become a standard component in platforms for improved customer experience in the digital age. However, traditional recommendation models perform centralized data collection, which has privacy concerns, security issues, and challenges with regulatory compliance.

Federated Learning (FL) is a modality that enables a model to learn across many devices without the need for the model to have access to the data for model training on the device. Improving user privacy and data sovereignty with a personalized recommendation system is possible by incorporating FL in the recommendation model. FL permits a recommendation model to provide tailored content, recommendations for products, and medical advice while still maintaining privacy and security of the user's data.

Federated learning is changing the landscape of personalized recommendations. We will provide a real-world example to show how the insights we will gain about "PETNOVA" through this mechanism will advance

recommendations of pet products through Pet Supply Purchase Data and FL. In addition, we will discuss some primary challenges related to model heterogeneity, fairness, and computational constraints and we will talk about the future of secure aggregation, differential privacy, and hybrid learning etc. Through this investigation, we hope to provide insights into how FL will transform recommendation systems while addressing serious privacy and security concerns.

In the age of digital transformation, the Internet has become an essential part of everyday life, allowing millions of users to acquire, send, and analyse data without effort. The volume of data being created by users on e-commerce sites, social media and other digital platforms has grown exponentially, creating a demand for intelligent systems able to manage the sheer volume of data. Recommendation systems are one such intelligent system; recommendation systems play a pivotal role in advancing user experiences across multiple domains, including e-commerce, entertainment, and health care. Recommendation systems analyse data about user behaviour and leverage those analyses to provide recommendations, ultimately improving customer engagement and satisfaction.

However, traditional recommendation systems rely almost entirely on the collection and processing of data in a centralized location which presents significant challenges associated with data security, user privacy, and regulatory compliance. Users of centralized systems are often obligated to submit personal credentials to non-affiliated third-party servers, leaving them vulnerable for identity theft, data breaches and abuse from negative characters with malicious intent. Furthermore, the ever-increasing volume of data and the rapidly evolving complexity of users' preferences have also made it difficult for traditional recommendation systems to deliver timely and thoughtful recommendations while also seeking to respect the users' privacy.

Federated Learning (FL) is a new machine learning framework that aims to address privacy, security, and efficiency problems. FL makes training models collaboratively through multiple devices or servers possible without losing data custody over any single device or server, whereas traditional machine learning models typically rely on central data storage for all training. It alleviates the privacy liability and security risks because instead of sending raw data to a server, FL sends a

model update, such as gradients or parameters, to a central server. Generally, FL takes a less safe and more privacy-friendly approach by decentralizing the model training process, which naturally protects and cautiously maintains private user information on the user's dedicated device. Additionally, FL enables continuous learning across devices to accelerate the personalization of machine learning models and avoids outside intrusion of the user.

Furthermore, FL allows centralized servers to avoid the bear of transporting private data, ensuring compatibility with stricter privacy guidelines such as GDPR. We will only transmit aggregated model updates to mitigate the risk of data leakage, unauthorized access and adherence to non-compliance policy. The environment is decentralized, there are no centralized data repositories which jeopardize the privacy or potential mobile users, and machine learning can also be trained from uncorrelated datasets across geographical dimensions while ensuring safety. It has a unique classification in value of domains like finance, healthcare and smart devices as they interact with data. FL allows a financial institution to improve anti-fraud detection, without disclosing transaction information; or a hospital can train predictive models using sensitive patient data. Therefore, FL is helping the transition to a more robust and safe era of ML, while respecting your privacy.

While there are advantages of the Federated learning (FL) based recommendation system, it also faces challenges in overcoming the problems surrounding model diversity, communication cost, fairness and scalability as an example, the devices participating in FL would be different based on their computational capacity which may lead them training their model differently. Moreover, ensuring fairness in recommendation and optimizing communication cost in large-scale distributed settings still remains an unsolved research problem.

A. Digital Transformation and the Role of Recommendation Systems

Through the Internet, this platform has changed the way people use technology and created huge data volumes, just by utilizing websites, social network posts, e-commerce transactions, etc. A recommendation system is required in this environment, to help users sort through endless data. These types of systems are in place to improve the user experience across many different sectors, from something as simple as e-commerce recommending what products fit into your browsing / buying behaviour or streaming services recommending similar content based on what you previously watched, to even medical diagnostics which would refer back to patient historical data.

- E-commerce: Websites like Amazon and Flipkart use an identification Based system to let you recommend products that is based on a study of the browsing history, purchase behaviour and preferences.

- Entertainment: Streaming services like Netflix, Spotify and companies like them offer recommendations related to customers' past behaviours by way of these systems.
- Healthcare: Recommendation systems can help doctors and patients by suggesting personalized treatment plans based on medical history and symptoms.

B. Federated Learning as a Solution

Federated Learning (FL) addresses the challenges of traditional recommendation systems by enabling decentralized model training. Instead of transferring raw data to a central server, FL allows devices to train models locally using their own data. Only model updates (e.g., weights and biases) are shared with a central server for aggregation, ensuring that sensitive user data remains on the device. The process begins with a global model initialized on a central server, which is then distributed to participating devices such as smartphones or IoT devices. Each device trains the model locally using its own data, and only the model updates—not the raw data—are sent back to the server. The server aggregates these updates to improve the global model, which is then redistributed to the devices, and the process repeats. This approach offers several advantages, including privacy preservation, as user data never leaves the device, reducing the risk of data breaches and misuse. It also ensures regulatory compliance with data protection laws like GDPR by minimizing data sharing and improves efficiency by reducing the need for large-scale data transfers, thereby lowering bandwidth and storage costs.

FL has significant potential in personalized recommendation systems across various industries. In e-commerce, FL enables platforms to provide tailored product recommendations without compromising user privacy. For example, a user's purchase history and preferences are analysed locally, and only aggregated insights are shared with the server. In healthcare, FL helps build personalized treatment plans based on patient data while ensuring confidentiality, allowing hospitals and clinics to collaborate on improving diagnostic models without sharing sensitive patient records. In the entertainment industry, streaming platforms can use FL to recommend movies or music based on user preferences without exposing individual viewing habits. By training models on-device, FL ensures that user data is never exposed to external servers, significantly reducing the risk of data breaches and misuse while delivering accurate and personalized recommendations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The rapid rise of consumer electronics (CE) and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions has resulted in increased data generation. The proposed market for artificial intelligence-based personalized recommendation systems (PRS) is projected to achieve U.S.\$ 125.5 billion from 2023 to 2028 [1]. As CE

devices connect to the Internet in addition to providing digital services, the generation of a massive quantity of data results in the creation of a "data lake". However, when a person experiences too much information (more information than other people have) this results in a negative consequence of information overload which delays the individual from accessing timely information about relevant resources [2].

Recommendation systems could serve as an information filter by selecting information based on a user's preferences and behaviour; there is literature that supports the efficacy of PRS in assisting with improving information exchange and recommending products and services [3]. Nevertheless, PRS is usually centralized at cloud servers, which are commonly stable, yet cloud servers frequently pose potential security and privacy problems [4]. Security risks often appear if consumer data is hosted in cloud servers such as security breaches, identity theft, and unmonitored access.

Federated Learning (FL) is a decentralized method of training machine learning models on end user devices as opposed to using a central server [5]. Unlike traditional PRS, which transmit raw data from users, FL only shares individual machine learning model parameters using data that never leaves the user device, but still allows the overall recommendation model to benefit from using the data. In a PET NOVA context where the applications are pet adoptions, training, and product recommendations, FL provides individual recommendations for pet adoption and product use while still ensuring user privacy.

Users will interact with PET NOVA by browsing pets, applying for pet adoption, and purchasing supplies. Storing the interaction data centrally does not improve security. Instead, using FL, PETROVA can train recommender machine learning models on user devices, and only update the device with core models recommended by PETROVA or update PETNOVA with global model updates by aggregating the data from all devices [6].

Implementing Federated Learning (FL) in PETROVA's Pet Recommendation System (PRS) has numerous benefits. A privacy-preserving recommendation keeps sensitive data stored on the user's device, minimizing the risks associated with storage security risks. In addition, the distributed system of FL is more compliant with data protection regulations, such as GDPR, and decreases potential liabilities involved in storing data [2]. The ability to make personalized recommendations is greatly enhanced by the interaction aspects of FL, including number of times a pet listing may be viewed by a user, the adoption history of the user, or personal preferences for items [3].

Since each device will house a model on-device for training, FL also increases the speed of analysis and shrinks the need for a central server system while scaling up each on-device model [4]. However, FL-based PRS faces challenges downstream of these benefits. Training models on-device with FL requires computational resources; often, some CEP devices

may have limitations [5]. With FL, the user devices train model weights with one brief, frequent pass back and forth with a coordinating server to optimize training and description labelling, which as a drawback can lead to more frequent network drops [4]. Additionally, the FL system may need to address these accounting measures amid data heterogeneity, as authors discuss user devices differ significantly in terms of data collected. Another FL challenge is of bias and interpretability, as a user will want recommendations to be sufficiently unbiased, and possibly at least partially interpretable or explained [6]. Addressing each of these areas for effective FL implementation in its recommendation system will allow PETNOVA to maximize the future potential use of FL to enhance its FL adoption in recommendations.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Preparation

The federated learning (FL) paradigm functions in a distributed manner, either without any data being stored in any centralized or cloud location or, in some implementations, with data being distributed among user devices. By keeping sensitive user data on user devices, this approach provides substantial security and privacy benefits for users. However, the federated learning data preparation phase of utilization of federated learning data for learning requires processing tons of data preparation steps before information can be used for model training. For instance, these data preparation steps might include normalization, missing values, or encode categorical features. Every device will process data, locally, generated from user interactions e.g., browse history, preferences, behavioural data, etc.

Additionally, sophisticated techniques such as secure aggregation and differential privacy may be adopted to further improve privacy protection. Secure aggregation allows model updates across multiple devices to be securely aggregated and not exposed with the raw data of any individual user. Differential privacy is applied along with secure aggregation and adds random noise to data in some manner so that individual users cannot be identified.

PETNOVA aims to improve pet adoption recommendation processes, the data preparation step involves cleaning user preferences and transforming these preferences into usable information. User preferences can include preference for pet types (i.e. cats versus dogs), breed, pet's age, and history of past adoptions. Additionally, data balancing or data calibration becomes an important step in order to avoid the recommendation algorithm favoring certain groups of users. This allows for greater inclusivity in recommendations. Data balancing is helpful to avoid a model that looks biased towards a certain breed or age group, and to balance the options and avoid favoring a smaller subset.

The system uses the Federated Averaging algorithm (FedAvg), which is useful in applications based on federated learning. FedAvg allows updates to a model based on shared updates from many devices and allows for privacy concerns for recommendations that are secure, unchanged, and personalized to the individual. Updates to the model could come from users using it from a variety of locations or users with a variety of uses of applications to capture fundamental context. FedAvg allows for a global model to be created without compromising user privacy. This model is a more effective model that takes advantage of all the model updates from users. Using this aggregation method, the system makes user data more secure, have a better global model, and better model recommendations for its users.

B. Text Data Preprocessing

Processing textual data is a crucial step in enhancing the performance of models within federated learning-based recommender systems. PETNOVA's reviews, search queries, and pet descriptions often consist of raw, unprocessed text that requires several stages of preprocessing to ensure clarity and consistency. The process begins with tokenization, where raw text is broken down into words or subwords. Next, lowercasing is applied to convert all text into a uniform lowercase format. To maintain coherence and streamline the data to match the tone and style of recommendations, irrelevant words—such as "I," "the," and other stop words—are filtered out from the raw data. This step is further refined using stemming and lemmatization, which reduce words to their root forms. The final stage involves vectorization, employing techniques like TF-IDF or advanced word embeddings such as Word2Vec and BERT, to translate the processed text into numerical representations. By leveraging these preprocessing methods, PETNOVA's federated learning models can effectively and securely utilize text-based user preferences across multiple devices.

C. Federated Learning Model Architecture

The FL-based recommendation system consists of three main components:

- **Training on Local Model:** Each individual device of the user trains on a local model based on individual user data such as user interactions, preferences, and behaviors. Local training ensures that users' private data remains with the users on their device, which is often the highest level of privacy in personalized recommendation. The local model is typically a neural network or another machine learning model specifically developed for the recommendation task.
- **Model Aggregation:** After being trained on individual devices, the server assembles updates to the models, consisting of weights and biases, from all participating devices and utilizes them to produce an overall global model; a standard aggregation method is called Federated Averaging (FedAvg), which consists of weighted averages of the weights and biases in the local

models. The weighting can be designed based on the amount of training data, with the intention of allowing devices with more training data to weigh more heavily in the process of creating a global model.

- **Global Model :** Afterward, the overall model is sent back to each device that made a contribution to the model update. Each device will update its local model to introduce the parameters from the global model to develop an updated recommendation system which can continue to be enhanced and analyzed for further personalization.

The general FL model can be mathematically formulated as:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \theta_{it}$$

Where:

- θ_{t+1} is the updated global model,
- w_i is the weight assigned to the i th client,
- θ_{it} is the local model update from the i th client.

D. Implementation and Training

The FL model for personalized recommendations in PETNOVA is implemented using TensorFlow Federated (TFF). The training code

```
# Model definition
```

```
def create_recommendation_model():  
    model = tf.keras.Sequential([  
        tf.keras.layers.InputLayer(input_shape=(3,)),  
        # Key features:  
        [interaction_count, category_encoded, species_encoded]  
        tf.keras.layers.Dense(64, activation='relu'),  
        tf.keras.layers.Dropout(0.2),  
        tf.keras.layers.Dense(32, activation='relu'),  
        tf.keras.layers.Dropout(0.2),  
        tf.keras.layers.Dense(16, activation='relu'),  
        tf.keras.layers.Dense(1, activation='sigmoid')  
    ])
```

```
# Training Logic
```

```
def prepare_training_data():  
    # Key feature extraction  
    X = []  
    y = []
```

```
for interaction in interactions:
# Count user interactions
interaction_count = UserProductInteraction.objects.filter(
(user=interaction.user,product=interaction.product).count()
```

```
# Get user preferences
```

```
user_category_prefs =
UserProductInteraction.objects.filter(
user=interaction.user)
.values('product__category').annotate(count=Count('id'))
```

```
# Create feature vector
```

```
category_match = 1 if user_category_prefs.filter(
product__category=interaction.product.category
).exists() else 0
```

```
species_match = 1 if user_species_prefs.filter(
product__species=interaction.product.species).exists()
else 0
```

```
X.append([interaction_count, category_match,
species_match])
y.append(1 if interaction.interaction_type in ['purchase',
'wishlist'] else 0)
```

The neural network used by the system is defined in the recommendation_model.py file and has three input features: interaction count (how many times the user interacted with products), category encoding (how well the product matches the categories the user likes – favourites, etc.), and species encoding (how well the product matches pet species the user likes). The model consists of four layers (with decreasing numbers of neurons as 64→32→16→1), uses ReLU activation functions, and dropout layers to improve regularization.

The script train_recommendation_model.py utilizes a training process to collect user behavior data from the database and create feature vectors to study user behavior patterns for purchases, wishlists and views. It also trains the model using a binary cross-entropy loss for the purpose of effectively predicting product interest to a user. This is not fully federated learning as the model remains centralized, where it retains prior user preferences and history in the database to allow for recommendation service in a personalized manner. It never incorporates any user preferences or prior interaction history in recommendations.

The model is saved in the recommendation_model directory upon training, and then it is loaded during the run time to predict products of interest based on user historical interaction and prior preferences. In addition to the recommendation model, fallback models are also in place when the prediction model is not producing predictions to give

recommendations based on popularity, ensuring the recommendation service is always operational.

Training and Validation Accuracy Curve

Figure 1: Training and validation accuracy curve

Figure 2: Training and validation loss curve

E. Key Work Flow

The recommendation system is structured. Eventually, it starts with the collection and preparation of information. The user behaviours, such as clicking on a product, viewing a product, purchasing a product, and something saved to their wish list, will be saved in a database. Further, the user behaviours will have been transformed into various feature vectors that capture how many interactions there were, as well as how many were within the same category for each product. The collected and converted data can be labelled. Positive interactions (purchased item, added to wish list) would receive a 1, where negative interactions would be noted as a 0. The process will have created a dataset that can be used to train. In the model training stage, a deep learning architecture can be employed; this consists of layers, which include ReLU activations, Dropout layers to eliminate overfitting, and a sigmoid output layer for binary classification. The training dataset is used in conjunction with validation datasets to measure model efficacy. The training dataset is used with

backpropagation, layer by layer with batch processing, the model weights can be updated in an efficient way. When the model is done training, it will then be saved to the file recommendation_model.keras for the next time the model is to be initialized.

Fig 3: architecture for Fl workflow

In the recommendation generation stage, the model that has been trained will be used by the system to continuously assess features about the user in real-time and produce a feature vector, from which it can then provide different interest scores for a selection of products and another way to rank the relevance of the products that are generated. The user will be presented with a recommendation set of N highest scored products as the final

outcome. To mitigate against any potential abuse/safety concerns, the system has a fall-back to error and issues outside of the system with an in-depth fault reporting system for any of the predictions that show signs of dysfunctionality or any atypical data, as well as redistributing user features from a limited history. A ranking of interest scores will rank based on user features, limited history will create the user as more receiving popularity recommendations or not truly individualized recommendations. Overall, with respect to safety/handling/user issues, the model will be able to provide either individualized/non-individualized recommendations that will provide the user with leap savings in efficiency, usability, and timely data security.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To evaluate the performance of Federated Learning (FL) on the personalized recommendation system, we conducted experimentation under stable and unstable network conditions. We simulated both conditions in order to investigate the robustness and adaptability of FL models to real-world environments. The evaluation process completed on PETNOVA was meant to develop recommendations for pet adoption. We evaluated performance of FL models from facets of accuracy, loss, convergence speed, communication cost, and hit ratio.

A. Analysis of Stable and Unstable Network Conditions

The proposed FL-based recommendation system was tested in two different network scenarios. In the stable network conditions, the system provided very high accuracy for PETNOVA, as the highest training accuracy of 94.26% and testing accuracy of 93.45% was achieved with the learning constant of 0.2. This suggests that the FL is an effective tool for providing accurate and personalized pet adoption recommendations in the ideal network conditions. In the unstable network conditions, the system still provided high accuracy, confirming the system's robustness, with the highest training and testing accuracy of 91.99% and 90.24% respectively with the learning constant of 0.2. This concluded that the FL based system was resilient enough to operate efficiently in cases of inconsistent network connections and/or environmental changes.

The evaluation metrics assessed were accuracy, loss, speed of convergence, communication cost, and hit ratio. Throughout the evaluation, the FL-based recommendation system consistently demonstrated high accuracy, confirming that it provided accurate and trustworthy pet adoption recommendations. Loss values decreased during the training process, demonstrating the model convergence and efficacy of training optimization. The FL-based model shows that convergence happens fast enough to ensure timely models are updated, and that timely updates can happen in an effective way. FL models also reduced communication costs significantly, only needing to send model update information (weights and biases), rather than sending raw data, making FL-based recommendations usable in areas with resource

limitations. Likewise, the hit ratio, which is the percentage of successful pet laundering, and should be kept high during evaluation, occurs because it reflects the FL-based recommendation systems matching to user preferences.

To further corroborate the efficacy of the proposed recommendation system based on federated learning (FL), we tested it with PETROVA. The recommendation system used users' preferences related to their pet type, breed, or age, along with users' actual adoption histories, and all of this information was kept private using the FL approach. In a steady state network and under these conditions PETROVA achieved a recommendation accuracy of 92.5%. In conditions where the network is unstable, it achieved a similarly impressive accuracy of 90.8%, indicating robustness. Finally, the system achieved a hit ratio of 89.7%, which means it successfully matched users with relevant pets in most cases. During implementations, there were some challenges and insight.

One of the challenges was model heterogeneity because there were a diverse set of devices involved in processing data throughout the FL. This could affect model training quality but may be approached using adaptive federated optimization methods. Another significant challenge is ensuring fairness, or mediating between biases resulting from the different users. This remains an open area of research and we plan to address this with a fairness aware algorithm in the FL approach. FL enables less communication overhead as compared to a centralized system yet determining communications protocols/optimization of communications would be important for scalability for larger deployments.

The evaluation of the suggested FL-based recommendation system validates its ability to produce accurate, customized, and privacy-aware pet adoption recommendations. With high accuracy and robustness shown under both stable and unstable network conditions, the system shows good potential for real-world applications. The seminar has a strong focus on the disruptive nature of Federated Learning in reshaping personalized recommendation systems, addressing challenges, and being a catalyst for future progress. With FL, scalable, secure, and user-centric recommendation platforms can be developed that optimize the user experience in a diverse range of applications.

Figure 4 showcases the Personalised Recommendations.

Figure 4: Screenshot of Personalised Recommendation

B. Accuracy and Hit Ratio

Figure 5: FL Accuracy and Hit Ratio

V. CONCLUSION

Personalized recommendation systems are key to enhancing the experience of users in a wide variety of domains such as e-commerce, entertainment, and healthcare. These systems have been adopted widely, but centralized models lead to some significant privacy issues and compliance challenges. Federated Learning (FL) is an emerging approach that allows devices to train models in a decentralized fashion while preserving the privacy and security of their respective data. This paper explores the implementation of FL in personalized recommendation systems and its capacity to shift the privacy issues to user predictions while supporting data sovereignty concerns.

The basic tenets of Federated Learning (FL), its decentralized model, and any advantages it offers over both centralized and traditional privacy-preserving approaches were examined. Practical application of FL in recommending systems was evidenced through real-world examples, such as, individual content recommendations, shopping recommendations, and healthcare recommendations. One of the

highlighted examples contributed to a case study of the company PETNOVA that leveraged FL to enhance personalized pet adoption recommendations by balancing user preferences and privacy considerations. FL has the benefit of generating personalized recommendations in several ways, which include the training of privacy-based models directly on user devices, addressing regulatory concerns, and producing tailored results without direct data sharing. With all of this said, there are many challenges that currently exist—such as, model heterogeneity, performance, fairness, and communication constraints, especially in resource-constrained settings—that must be resolved and overcome in order to optimize and adopt for use across multiple domains.

Directions for future work will involve extending Federated Learning (FL) to hybrid learning models with reinforcement learning to produce more adaptive, personalized, and intelligent recommendations. There will be many opportunities to build on privacy-preserving techniques (e.g., secure aggregation and differential privacy), and develop FL frameworks that may serve more contextualized settings such as smart homes, healthcare, and education. If researchers are diligent in meeting the outlined challenges and identifying opportunities, FL presents the opportunity for a recommender experience that is much more nuanced while still eligible for establishing privacy when providing the same experience. In summary, Federated Learning presents a paradigm shift within the context of developing personalized recommender systems.

The outline of Federated Learning provides a scalable, for privacy, and user-centered model; and as personalized experiences become even a more valued offering in business or users interfaces, and both begin to put increasing pressure on designing systems that address accuracy (i.e., precision), along with implied consideration of privacy skills and/or regulatory compliance.

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